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Transformation of business models of educational services in the conditions of globalization

Hanyu Du

PhD student of the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education, Department of Management, Business and Administration, Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics, Nauky Ave. 9a, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61165, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3988-0987>

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***Abstract.** The article reveals the essence of transformational processes in educational services caused by globalization's influence. It is determined that the modern education system is under pressure from many globalization factors, in particular, digitalization, internationalization, changing labor market needs, and growing competition in the educational services market. In this context, the need to rethink and modify traditional business models in education, which were focused mainly on offline formats and the hierarchical structure of knowledge management, is becoming more urgent.*

The paper presents a typology of business models of educational services, classified into traditional, electronic, and mixed. A list of types of business models within each type is systematized. Each model type's key characteristics, advantages, and limitations in the context of globalization challenges are determined. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of mixed models as the most promising in modern

conditions, allowing the flexibility of the digital environment to be combined with the pedagogical effectiveness of classical educational formats.

The study's methodological basis is a systematic, comparative, and structural-functional approach. The article also uses scientific literature analysis and classification methods. It is substantiated that the effective transformation of education business models requires the introduction of innovations, establishing partnerships with the private sector, and increasing the flexibility of management in educational organizations.

It is concluded that the future of business models in education will be determined by the education system's ability to respond to global challenges and proactively form a new educational ecosystem based on innovation, openness, and sustainable development.

Keywords. *Business model, educational service business model, digitalization, globalization, transformation, digitalization.*

Трансформація бізнес-моделей освітніх послуг в умовах глобалізації

Ханьюй Ду

здобувач третього (освітньо-наукового) рівня вищої освіти, кафедра менеджменту, бізнесу і адміністрування, Харківський національний економічний університет імені Семена Кузнеця, просп. Науки 9а, м. Харків, Україна, 61165, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3988-0987>

Анотація. *У статті розкрито сутність трансформаційних процесів у сфері надання освітніх послуг, обумовлених впливом глобалізаційних змін. Визначено, що сучасна система освіти перебуває під тиском багатьох факторів глобалізації, зокрема цифровізації, інтернаціоналізації, зміни потреб ринку праці та зростаючої конкуренції на ринку освітніх послуг. У цьому контексті актуалізується потреба у переосмисленні та модифікації*

традиційних бізнес-моделей в сфері освіти, що були орієнтовані переважно на офлайн-формати та ієрархічну структуру управління знанням.

У роботі проведено типологізацію бізнес-моделей освітніх послуг, класифікованих на традиційні, електронні та змішані. Систематизовано перелік видів бізнес-моделей в рамках кожного типу. Визначено ключові характеристики кожного типу моделей, їхні переваги та обмеження в контексті глобалізаційних викликів. Особливу увагу приділено аналізу змішаних моделей як найперспективніших у сучасних умовах, що дозволяють поєднувати гнучкість цифрового середовища з педагогічною ефективністю класичних освітніх форматів.

Методологічну основу дослідження становлять системний, порівняльний та структурно-функціональний підходи. У статті також використано методи аналізу наукової літератури та класифікації. Обґрунтовано, що ефективна трансформація бізнес-моделей освіти потребує впровадження інновацій, налагодження партнерств із приватним сектором, а також підвищення гнучкості управління в освітніх організаціях.

Підсумовано, що майбутнє бізнес-моделей у сфері освіти визначатиметься здатністю системи освіти не лише реагувати на глобальні виклики, а й проактивно формувати нову освітню екосистему, засновану на інноваціях, відкритості та стійкому розвитку.

***Ключові слова:** бізнес-модель, бізнес-модель освітньої послуги, цифровізація, глобалізація, трансформація, діджиталізація.*

Statement of the problem. In the current conditions of globalization, the education sector is undergoing significant transformations due to the intensification of international knowledge exchange, the development of digital technologies, the growth of student mobility, and changing labor market demands. Traditional business models focused mainly on providing full-time education services are gradually losing their effectiveness and competitiveness in global education. In this regard, the

relevance of implementing new, flexible models that combine innovative digital solutions, adaptability to changes in the external environment, and a customer-oriented approach is increasing.

Despite the growing number of digital platforms, online courses, international educational collaborations, and hybrid learning formats, scholars and practitioners have not yet developed a unified approach to classifying modern business models in education.

Thus, a comprehensive scientific analysis of the transformation processes of educational services' business models and their typology is needed, as well as for identifying factors that influence the success of adapting educational services to the challenges of globalization.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In transforming business models in education, scientists pay significant attention to innovative approaches to organization educational services. Thus, Christensen K., Horn M., and Johnson K. in [1] emphasize that the traditional education system does not meet the modern requirements of personalized learning and requires "destructive" changes, which consist of introducing digital technologies and the creation of new models of educational services. Other scientists hold a similar opinion, in particular, Okoli Ch., Wang N. [2], which indicates the need to adapt the business models of educational institutions to the hybrid learning format and implement models focused on long-term interaction with the student through digital platforms.

Research devoted to the commercialization of education and its integration into the global market occupies a separate niche in the scientific discussion. Thus, Siladius I.'s work [3] explores the challenges for national education systems related to competition from international educational platforms (Coursera, edX). Researchers in the works [4, 5] emphasize the importance of developing adaptive business models that combine local features with global trends.

Scientists in their works [3, 4] also investigate and identify various factors of globalization that become an impetus for the transformation of business models in the field of education.

Despite the relatively extensive coverage in the scientific literature of issues related to the adaptation of business models in the field of educational services, a number of important aspects remain insufficiently explored. In particular, at the current stage of educational environment development, the types of business models used in the education sector have not been adequately substantiated from a theoretical and methodological perspective, nor has their clear systematization been carried out. The lack of classification complicates the practical application of business models that are focused on innovative approaches to the provision of educational services. In this regard, there is a pressing need to identify the key characteristics of each type of business model in the context of globalization challenges.

Formulation of the article's goals (task statement): The study aims to substantiate and generalize modern business models of educational services theoretically and determine the directions of their transformation in the context of globalization.

Presentation of the primary research material. The study of business model transformation in educational services is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines economic theory, management theory, pedagogy, and digital economy. The theoretical basis of the analysis is the concepts of the business model proposed by Osterwalder A. and Pigneur Y. [6], as structures for creating, delivering, and capturing value, as well as modern approaches to studying educational platforms in the context of digital transformation, which were investigated by Christensen S. [1] and Okoli Ch. [2]. Zelenin Yu. [7] notes that an effective business model is the key to successfully implementing all organizational processes; therefore, the author highlights the principle of universality, according to which the business model covers all areas of the enterprise's functioning.

The works of Christensen S., Okoli Ch., Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y., Zelenin Yu., Shvydanenko G., Revutska N., Velichko K., Tsybulska E., Rof A., Bikfalvi A., Gou PM and others are devoted to the study of business models [1-2, 6-10].

In their scientific research, Shvydanenko G., Revutska N., Yurchyshena L., Christensen C., Horn M., and Johnson C. [1, 8, 11] consider traditional business models that can be adapted to the education sector. It should be noted that conventional business models of educational services were formed in the conditions of an industrial economy and are characterized by centralized management, hierarchical structure, orientation to offline learning formats, and long-term academic cycles. Such models involve providing educational services offline within a physical campus, focusing on the internal processes of the educational service provider, a classical program, and public or mixed financing [1].

The key characteristics of the traditional model are the presence of permanent teaching staff, regulated curricula, an administrative vertical of management, and limited interaction with the labor market or consumers of educational services in real time. As noted by Trow M. [12], the traditional business model operates within the concept of "the university as an autonomous institute of knowledge", where the educational process is organized primarily according to the logic of academic tradition rather than economic efficiency.

Clark B. [13] emphasizes that classical universities traditionally do not perceive themselves as market actors but as public institutions with educational and cultural missions. In such a model, funding sources typically include government grants, tuition fees, and charitable contributions. Profit is not a priority, significantly distinguishing it from modern flexible or platform models.

In the domestic context, the issue of the traditional business model in the field of education was considered in the works of Yurchyshena L. [11] and Zelenin Y. [7], who emphasize the limitations of classical structures in the context of digital transformation. The authors argue that despite its stability, the traditional model

demonstrates low adaptability to environmental changes, making it vulnerable to globalization and digitalization.

One of the priority areas of education development in the context of globalization, as noted by Voinalovich O. [14], is the introduction of modern digital technologies that ensure the improvement of the educational process, the accessibility and effectiveness of education, and the development of digital competencies among education seekers. As stated in [15], the digitalization of education plays a vital role in developing education in the face of global challenges. The COVID-19 pandemic and martial law in Ukraine have proven the importance and necessity of digital technologies for the population's well-being and economic development.

Thus, in modern conditions of digitalization, the traditional business model of educational services, despite its stability and long-term effectiveness, needs to be reconsidered. That is why electronic business models have been developed, the research of which is devoted to the works of Okoli Ch., Du H., Mazorenko O., Velichko K., Tsybul'ska E., Rof A., Bikfalvi A., Gou P. [2, 9, 10, 15].

Electronic business models (e-models, digital) in education respond to the rapid development of information and communication technologies and society's digital transformation. They are based on using digital platforms to create, deliver, and monetize educational content. Unlike the traditional model, where learning is mainly offline, electronic models provide a completely remote format with flexible access to resources anytime and anywhere globally [16].

The key types of electronic business models are distinguished [2] as follows: models based on MOOCs (massive open online courses), subscription platforms (Coursera Plus, Udemy for Business), freemium models (free basic access with paid extensions), and models with the sale of certificates or licenses, etc. Such models allow you to scale educational services to a global audience.

According to research by Christensen S. [1], e-models contribute to democratizing access to knowledge and create conditions for increased participation in higher education, especially among adult students and professionals. At the same

time, they provoke discussions about the quality of teaching, the authenticity of assessment, and the lack of interactivity.

The leading providers of educational e-models are global platforms—Coursera, edX, FutureLearn, and Khan Academy—which operate on a partnership model with universities. They provide access to courses from leading teachers, often free or with a minimal fee for a certificate [17]. They actively use learning personalization algorithms, user behavior analytics, and artificial intelligence to adapt content, which significantly increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

Thus, electronic business models form a new paradigm of educational services based on innovation, flexibility, scalability, and end-user orientation, fundamentally changing the educational market landscape in the context of globalization.

Blended or hybrid business models in education combine elements of traditional and e-learning models, creating synergies between offline and online components of the educational process. This model is based on blended learning, combining face-to-face teaching with digital platforms for support of distance learning [18].

As noted by Picciano A., Dziuban C., and Graham C. in [19], blended business models in education are particularly effective in globalization, where the need for flexible learning is increasing while maintaining the value of personal interaction between teacher and student. For example, universities can offer introductory courses online while practical classes, laboratories, or seminars remain offline. This approach allows you to reduce infrastructure costs while maintaining the quality of educational services.

According to the study [20], hybrid business models create new opportunities for personalizing learning, providing an adaptive approach to learning styles, and improving educational process analytics. In addition, such models are supported by a growing number of EdTech solutions that allow the integration of digital tools into educational programs without disrupting traditional learning structures [15].

Blended business models are also successfully implemented in business education and corporate training, where combining synchronous and asynchronous formats increases the efficiency of training specialists [21]. As noted by Okoli Ch., Wang N. in [2], blended business models demonstrate positive outcomes in academic performance and student satisfaction compared to both traditional and e-business models.

Thus, hybrid models act as strategically balanced business solutions that allow educational institutions to adapt to digital transformation while maintaining the key advantages of a live educational environment.

As a result of the content analysis of scientific sources [1-2, 7-13, 18-19], a typology of educational service business models was systematized, which involves dividing them into three main groups: traditional (offline models, typical of classical HEIs), electronic (digital, associated with distance education and platform solutions), and mixed (hybrid models, combining the features of the first two) (Fig. 1). Such a division allows us to more accurately assess the dynamics of changes in the field of educational services depending on the level of digitalization, internationalization and flexibility of organizational structures.

As previous studies show, educational institutions are increasingly integrating elements of the platform economy and expanding their presence in the digital environment. This indicates a gradual change in the concept of "educational service" and the transformation of educational service business models in the context of globalization.

Globalization significantly affects the functioning of the education system in general and the business models of educational services in particular. As noted in [5], the main factors of globalization that affect the education sector include digitalization, personalization of learning, the growth of online education, the integration of 21st-century skills (critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration), and the internationalization of educational programs. Such trends force us to rethink traditional approaches to the organization and provision of educational services.

Traditional business models	Electronic (digital) business models	Blended (hybrid) business models
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional Schools & Universities • Tutoring Centers / Special Courses • Corporate Training • Franchise Business Model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donation and Grant Model • Online Program of a Traditional Educational Institution • Advertising Model • Co-Production Consortium • Institutional Subscription • Sale of Course Experience • Subscription Model • Free Limited Access Model • Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) • Virtual Schools and Online Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community-based model • Government or foundation sponsorship • Syndication • Hybrid corporate learning • Blended learning in traditional educational institutions • Educational franchises with digital extensions • Subscription-based EdTech with offline events

Fig. 1. Typology of business models of an educational service

Source: systematized by the author based on [1-2, 7-13, 18-19]

One of globalization's key challenges is the increasing competition between universities in the international market for educational services. This necessitates the implementation of flexible, innovative, and customer-oriented business models that allow adapting to changes in demand, demographic changes, digital trends, and new forms of communication with students.

Digitalization, as a structural component of globalization, is significantly transforming the logic of the educational business. It allows you to scale educational services, automate administrative processes, and personalize learning through big data, artificial intelligence, and cloud technologies. According to Christensen C. [1], digitalization has become the driver of disruptive innovations that are changing the channels of knowledge delivery and the value of educational offerings.

In response to globalization's challenges, business model transformation is becoming strategic. Educational providers are increasingly moving from traditional financing through government subsidies to market-oriented models, where revenue sources are diversified and customer-centricity becomes a key principle. As scholars note in [22], the latest business models in education are characterized by openness, flexibility, and innovation in creating, delivering, and monetizing value.

Conclusions. Thus, globalization processes are a powerful driver of the structural transformation of educational service business models. They determine the shift in emphasis from static institutional structures to dynamic, adaptive, and competitive models of providing educational services in a global environment.

In turn, the development of blended models that combine traditional and electronic elements allows educational systems to be adapted to the diverse needs of target audiences, increasing their inclusiveness and effectiveness.

In addition, a promising direction is the expansion of cooperation between universities and the private sector, particularly EdTech companies, which creates opportunities for developing innovative partnership models.

Thus, the education system's ability to respond to global challenges and proactively shape a new educational ecosystem based on innovation, openness, and sustainable development will determine the future of business models in education.

Thus, the study's methodological basis allows us to identify the logic of changes in educational service business models, understand the driving forces of transformation, and outline the directions for adapting educational institutions to the new realities of the globalized educational space.

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